

Utilization of Whey Protein as Whey Ice Candy Produce Bioactive Peptides and Reduce Its Antigenicity

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In this study, reduce the antigenicity of whey protein using the digestive enzyme it's the way whey ice candy has been preparing. Pepsin enzyme was used for hydrolysis and produce bioactive peptide-like ACE-inhibitor, an opioid peptide which is beneficial for cardiovascular health, nervous system, improve digestibility system, increases metal-binding ability, anti- appetizing and boost immunity. It is containing fruit juices and sugar which will increase the palatability of whey candy. According to the consumer acceptability test of whey, ice candy was successfully accepted in the market.

Keywords: Whey protein, Whey ice candy, Bioactive peptide, Antigenicity

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INTRODUCTION

Whey poses a major worldwide disposal problem in the dairy industry and whey is a by-product it is a good source of lactose, mineral, a water-soluble vitamin, and most important bioactive peptide. Why proteins are not fully hydrolyzing by the digestive system because of presence in di-sulfide bond and other barriers in whey which causes antigenicity in the digestive system.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of whey protein offers a practical way to decrease its antigenicity and it furthermore produces bioactive peptide which beneficial for human and consumption as an infant formula. Now enzymatic hydrolysis is an effective and dependable method to produce peptides with antihypertensive, antithrombotic, antioxidant, anticancer, immunomodulatory, and most important is opioid and anti-inflammatory activities. Digestive enzymes like industrial pepsin are utilized to break large polypeptide into particular little peptide and their movement depending upon their amino acid composition and sequence total eleven synthetic peptides derived from theatrical release from β -Lg and α -La hydrolysis by pepsin β -Lg f(15-20), f(55-60), f(84-91), f(92-105), f(139-148), f(142-148) and α -La f(10-16) stimulated expansion to distinctive extents, while β -Lg f(15-20), f(55-60), and f(139-148) also initiated different inhibiting and/or stimulating impacts on cytokine emission (1) and hydrolysis of whey protein has been utilization to modify solubility, viscosity, emulsifying, and frothing properties, as well as to improve nutritional properties and its ideal for whey ice candy. Normally fruits pulp are accepted to improve natural the resistance of the body against disease and their immune-modulatory have been reported in several studies but due to their undesirable and sour or unpalatable test their health benefit cannot be completely utilized, particularly in the case of children but reduce its sourness by sugar and whey ice candy very attractive and palatable product for children as well as women in India and production of whey candy by addition of natural pulp juice can fulfill the requirement of ice candy in the modern market of India.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Raw material

Whey was obtained from household paneer producer whereas fruits like pineapple, orange were procured from bad fruits market while sugar and food-grade color was purchased from shiv general store and in addition, CMC was purchased from ice cream Stabilizer Pvt. Ltd.

Extraction of fruit juice

First of all, wash pineapple and orange fruits with normally warm water and then pilling and coring, crushing, pulping, and filtration with help of muslin cloth, generally bucket type filter is used in the PHE unit.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of whey

The digestive enzyme pepsin is used for hydrolysis of clarified (5900rpm) whey. Increase the temperature of whey at 40°C and pass through clarifier it helps removed dust and other foreign matter. After that add food grade HCL to maintain pH-2 for activation of pepsin. Pepsin was adding 1% of whey. Inactivation of pepsin by pasteurization of whey at 90°C for 10 minutes holding and cooled it at homogenization temperature. Neutralization was done by soda base at pH-4.6

Methodology

Initially enzymatic hydrolyze whey are mix with fruit juice like pineapple and orange (10-20%), mixed sugar (25-30%), CMC stabilizer (0.3%) it's low as compared to normal whey ice candy because after hydrolysis viscosity of whey is increased. Proper mix with agitator then candy mix is pass through homogenizer at 159kg/cm² its help to improve body and texture of candy and ingredients are completely mixed and reduce the size of ice crystal and re-pasteurization of whey candy mix, molding in proper quantity as per requirement. Transfer into blast room for hardening, the temperature of blast room is minimum -200 for proper hardening

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Physical properties

Generally, increases viscosity, thickness, gel formation in whey due to enzymatic hydrolysis it's favorable for the manufacturing of ice candy. The melting point of whey candy was decreased 42.93 to 40.84 due to a long-lasting storage period (2)

Chemical properties

Enzymatic hydrolysis of whey protein offers a practical way to decrease its antigenicity (3), including the amino acid grouping of peptides that exhibit in vitro ACE-inhibiting activity or in vivo antihypertensive impacts on the human body (4) and maintain blood pressure. Produce bioactive peptide-like antihypertensive, antioxidative, antithrombotic is beneficial for the cardiovascular system when opioid peptide for a nervous system for human health. Improve digestive system by increases mineral-binding ability, anti-appetizing, and boost the immune system by immunomodulatory and cytomodulatory. The pH of whey candy was decreased

Due to increases its storage periods and increase acidity 0.28 to 0.59 It could be due to inherited acidity present within the pulp and comes about the arrangement of organic acids by the degradation of ascorbic acid and utilization of sugar to yield organic acid.

CONSUMER ACCEPTABILITY STUDY

This test was performing on 80 people and provided an optimum sample of whey ice candy and hedonic scale card (range is 1 to 10) for measurement of overall acceptability of whey ice candy and conduct review of a product like flavors, test, color. The average result of the hedonic scale is 7.1 and it's acceptable in the market.

Conclusion

From the above study, it was concluding by-products of paneer and cheese whey in the dairy industry it was successfully utilization to manufacturing whey ice candy. It was observed to improve digestibility and reduce the antigenicity of whey by digestive enzyme, Produce bioactive peptide during hydrolysis is beneficial for cardiovascular health and the nervous system. Fruits juice and sugar was increases the palatability of whey candy. According to the consumer acceptability test for whey, candy was most attractive to small children, and the result of the hedonic test is acceptable to consumers.

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